

MULTIPARAMETRIC ULTRASOUND STUDY OF GLOMERULONEPHRITIS IN CHILDREN

¹Yusupaliyeva G.A., ²Sultanova L.R., ³Akhmedov E.A., ⁴Tolipova S.M.

^{1,2,3,4}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Glomerulonephritis (GN) is a group of diseases with immune-inflammatory damage to the glomeruli (Sethi S., 2012; Kronbichler A. et al., 2015; Couser W.G., 2016). The classical representative of the GN group is postinfectious GN (PIGN), which can have both acute and chronic courses. In 1/3 of cases, acute PIGN progresses to a chronic form. Chronic GN is a progressively worsening disease, and cases of recovery are rare. In countries with high socio-economic development, chronic GN ranks third among causes of chronic kidney disease (CKD), while in some Asian and African countries, it is the leading cause due to the high prevalence of infectious diseases and lack of conditions for effective treatment of diseases contributing to the development of GN (Ayodele O.E., Alebiosu C.O., 2010; Jha V. et al., 2013). In Uzbekistan, GN is a leading cause of terminal chronic renal failure, which is incompatible with life and requires expensive renal replacement therapy (dialysis, kidney transplantation) (Bikbov B.T., Tomilina N.A., 2016). Currently, for establishing the clinical course—acute and chronic GN—clinico-anamnestic data, general laboratory tests, blood and urine biochemical studies, radiological methods, and determination of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) are used (Mukhin N.A. et al., 2011).*

However, in clinical practice, there are often difficulties in the timely differentiation between acute GN and the exacerbation of chronic GN at the early stages of the disease due to the lack of specific diagnostic criteria. Chronic GN is usually diagnosed when significant, irreversible damage to the kidneys has already occurred with the development of nephrosclerosis, and the opportunity for timely diagnosis and treatment, which could prevent the progression of the pathological process in the kidneys, has been missed.

Keywords: *dialysis, kidney transplantation, echographic picture, pulsatility index (PI), hemodynamic parameters, glomerular filtration rate (GFR).*

Objective of the study. Evaluation of renal vascular hemodynamics in various clinical forms of glomerulonephritis in children.

Materials and methods. The study included 74 children with GN and 15 healthy children aged 3 to 18 years. The patients were hospitalized in the nephro-urology department of the National Medical Center for examination and treatment. The diagnosis was based on the classification adopted at the All-Union Symposium of Pediatric Nephrologists. All patients were examined while preserving renal function and were divided into three clinical groups. Group 1 consisted of children with nephrotic syndrome of acute GN (22 patients: 16 boys, 6 girls); Group 2 consisted of children with nephrotic syndrome and hematuria (9 patients: 5 boys, 4 girls); Group 3 consisted of children with nephrotic form of chronic GN (43 patients: 27 boys, 16 girls). Treatment for children with chronic GN was carried out in the nephrology department with differentiated therapy, considering the clinical form of the disease and the functional state of the kidneys, using traditional methods of pathogenetic therapy. A follow-up examination was conducted after remission was achieved.

In addition to clinical examination, paraclinical methods were used. Ultrasound examination (US) was performed on all patients dynamically, at various stages of kidney disease, and included a full examination of the abdominal organs in B-mode followed by triplex scanning of the kidneys, which included gray-scale imaging, flow cartography, and spectral analysis of blood flow. The examination was performed using an APLIO 500 ultrasound device, with a convex probe scanning at frequencies of 3.5 and 7.5 MHz. Peak systolic velocity (V_{ps}), end-diastolic velocity (V_{ed}), and time-averaged maximum blood flow velocity (T_{max}) in the renal artery trunk, segmental, interlobar, and arcuate arteries were determined. Given that the accuracy of measuring absolute blood flow velocities largely depends on the angle between the long axis of the vessel and the ultrasound beam, and it is difficult to control this for distal renal arteries, renal hemodynamics were assessed using "nearly angle-independent" indices—resistance index (RI) (norm 0.6-0.7), pulsatility index (PI) (norm 1.0-1.5), and systolic-to-diastolic ratio (S/D) (norm 2.5-3.5). A high degree of direct correlation was found between all three resistance indices ($r=0.92$; -0.96 , <0.05). The total examination time ranged from 15 to 35 minutes. No significant age-related differences were found among healthy children, so the average values obtained in the group were used.

Results. The analysis of Doppler ultrasound parameters showed that in all studied forms of GN, kidney hemodynamics were disturbed during the active phase of the disease. The most preserved blood flow was observed in patients with nephrotic acute GN. In this group, only at the level of the arcuate artery, kidney hemodynamics were slightly below the normal range. In larger arteries, they were not disturbed. In the analysis of Doppler ultrasound parameters during the active phase of GN without extrarenal manifestations, it was found that in acute GN, all resistance parameters at all levels of the renal artery remained almost within the normal range, except for a slight decrease in PI at the level of the arcuate artery. The echographic picture of chronic glomerulonephritis in gray-scale mode depended on the phase and duration of the disease. In the early stages, slight enlargement of the kidneys and a slight increase in parenchymal echogenicity were noted. More pronounced disturbances in the CDK parameters were observed: blood flow turbulence (31.3%), asymmetry in hemodynamic parameters (34.4%), localization of rare, thinned, and deformed vessels (6.3%), and diffuse reduction in vascularization (31.3%). In the analysis of velocity parameters in the active stage of chronic GN in children, disturbances were not observed in large vessels, but from the interlobar artery onward, blood flow velocity significantly decreased, particularly the diastolic blood flow velocity (V_d): 7.4 ± 0.08 mm/sec and 9.33 ± 0.28 mm/sec, respectively, $p < 0.05$. Additionally, an increase in the resistance index (RI) was observed (norm 0.6-0.7), amounting to 0.72 ± 0.04 in the renal artery trunk ($p < 0.05$), 0.65 ± 0.06 in the segmental artery ($p < 0.05$), 0.60 ± 0.04 in the interlobar arteries ($p < 0.05$), and 0.53 ± 0.04 in the arcuate artery ($p < 0.05$); pulsatility index (PI) (norm 1.0-1.5) was 1.47 ± 0.15 in the renal artery trunk, 1.22 ± 0.18 in the segmental artery, and 1.00 ± 0.10 in the interlobar arteries ($p < 0.05$); systolic-to-diastolic ratio (S/D) (norm 2.5-3.5) was 3.52 ± 0.39 in the renal artery trunk, 3.08 ± 0.39 in the segmental artery ($p < 0.05$), 2.41 ± 0.27 in the interlobar arteries ($p < 0.05$), and 2.24 ± 0.14 in the arcuate artery. In the absence of extrarenal manifestations, blood flow was predominantly impaired in the small (arcuate) arteries and characterized by a reduction in resistance index values. During the remission phase, the blood flow disturbances, in the form of reduced resistance indices, were only noted in the arcuate artery. No complete normalization of resistance indices was observed during remission (a slight decrease in indices was observed at the arcuate artery level).

Conclusion. Thus, according to Doppler ultrasound data, kidney blood flow in GN is disturbed at various levels of the renal artery (in the renal artery trunk, segmental, interlobar, and arcuate arteries). The most pronounced hemodynamic disturbances are observed in the small renal arteries—interlobar and especially arcuate arteries. In contrast, blood flow in larger arteries can remain normal.

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